

How Long Does Digital Trending Topic Last?: Study Case in Indonesia

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Abstract:- The internet has transformed the way people shop and think about what they buy. This, of course, motivates advertisers to be more forceful and innovative in the messages they generate, particularly in terms of how to use trends as an efficient input in deciding the overall topic and idea of the message that will be taken out. This article will examine how societal trends may be used as a successful input in building a brand's marketing plan. The study was conducted out by gathering data from five themes that became viral in Indonesia, utilizing Google Trends to collect data, and then analyzing then normalizing the data obtained. A topic that becomes viral on social media emerges swiftly, but it also fades quickly from user chats. A topic requires approximately three weeks to get to its climax. This presents a chance for marketers to take advantage of the ideal week to reach their communication targets, because the topic will begin to decline after that week and will not return to its peak. With limited time, a marketing initiative must be simple to the demographic being targeted to comprehend and deliver its own distinctiveness to capture the curiosity of their customers. Because no issue goes viral for an entire year, this stimulates creativity so that a new and timely marketing topic is generated on a quarterly basis to stay in the thoughts of consumers.

Keyword:- Market Trend, Google Trend, Viral Marketing.

I. INTRODUCTION

Technology has played an important role in the growth of marketing in digital media, there is increasingly significant two-way communication and determines the direction of purchasing from the target market. This two-way communication creates strong collaboration between consumers and brands [1]. Where currently the discussion that is taking place is also closely related to social media which cannot be separated from e-commerce [2].

Social commerce has become crucial currently [3]. Their shopping experience and how they determine purchasing direction are also greatly influenced by conversations in digital media [4]. Furthermore, today's consumers also see trends as one of their references when considering purchases.

Marketers are currently required to get to know their consumers better analytically, and knowing what the topics of conversation among them an advantage will be [5]. The

current development, through social commerce, is how the interaction process between [6].

Google Trends is an online web-based Google tool that tracks the ranking of search terms. Google Search is a global search engine with material in many different languages. Google Trend displays search results using time-dependent graphs and offers a variety of analytical features, including the ability to compare different search queries, track different words and phrases used in the Google search box, and categories and organize data with a focus on breaking it down by geographic location. Because Google Trends is mainly meant for advertisers, anybody can use it without restriction.

Google Trends is additionally used to forecast financial markets and economic indicators. Google Trends is being used more frequently in environmental and conservation studies. Examining patterns in public awareness and engagement regarding the preservation of biodiversity and other issues has been done using Google patterns data.

Furthermore, it has been demonstrated that Google Trends outperforms survey-based indicators. specifically, that Jeremy Ginsberg and co. This aligns with the average number of questions and the proportion of medical visits when patients come with influenza-like symptoms, demonstrating that Google Trends data may be utilized to track influenza-like disease in a population.

Marketing has changed along with accompanying technological developments. So that currently even strategic decisions are based on basic digital analytics that occur in the existing market ecosystem [7].

The internet has changed the way consumers shop and consider what they buy. This of course encourages marketers to be more aggressive and creative in the communication they develop [8], specifically how to observe trends as an effective input in determining the concept and theme of the communication that will be carried out.

This article will discuss how using trend developments occurring in society can be used as an effective input in developing a brand's marketing strategy. The research was carried out by observing data from five topics that had gone viral in Indonesia, collecting data using Google Trends and then processing and normalizing the data obtained.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

Analyzing the current state of digital marketing is the first topic that comes to mind when considering the key query that drives this inquiry. Businesses must monitor both market and marketing trends to perform marketing activities efficiently [9].

Concepts like internet advertising first became widely recognized during the start of the 1990s. The globalization of society, the information age, and the explosion of new technology are all currently everywhere and written websites that provided product information were simply the start of this innovation [10].

Therefore, a successful web marketing strategy must consider how potential customers speak and the language they might use. The planning of efficient search engine advertising techniques necessitates all these efforts, and by doing so, it is possible to develop a successful online relationship with customers [11].

Search engine optimization (SEO) is the practice of improving the exposure of a website and rating in results pages for search engines such Google, the more frequently you appear in the list of search results, the more traffic you will get from consumers of search engines [12], the higher your ranking on the result pages. The selection of keywords is a crucial and significant step in using search engine marketing effectively, and it necessitates paying close attention to the user's request's aim.

According to relevancy and prospective conversion rate, prominent keywords that relate to the content of the website are chosen for this process. Most search engines offer keyword recommendation tools that can be used to make this identification, or you can use information on popular terms. Website developers can position their web page at the top of the results by doing this since they can create a website that include some keywords that will enhance a better results and ROI. But frequent monitoring and updating of keywords is required [13] (Terrance et al., 2018).

The secret to effective internet marketing is thought to be content marketing, that can be produced by the brand itself or by the user generated content (UGC). Content marketing is a strategy that is centered on the production and of worthwhile, pertinent with the goal of attracting and keeping a certain audience and motivating a customer to take an action, such making a purchase. Since videos can be used as both a learning tool and a source of information, they have become increasingly popular in marketing communication methods [14]. (Sedej, 2019).

Nowadays, the key to effective marketing is to keep long-term relationships with customers by concentrating the strategy on their experiences. Videos encourage relationship and also creates awareness and engagement, and such entertaining, all of which are important in the contemporary corporate climate where innovative thinking and intelligence are prerequisites. Additionally, it can boost revenue, online traffic, brand exposure, and other things while increasing the target audience's understanding of the goods or services [14].

In determining a theme or concept for digital communication that will be carried out, our knowledge of current trends will give us good short-term profits. This is combined with developing personalization of messages to make them appear more original. Personalization is a fundamental idea in the field of marketing [15].

Personalization is a multi-stage process that requires iteration [16]. There are four stages in the process: customer recognition, needs identification, customer engagement, and product customization [17]. The concept of personalization can be broadly described as a process of co-creating value for consumers as well as marketers [18].

III. METHOD

This research was conducted quantitatively using data obtained from Google Trend based on five viral trends that have occurred in Indonesia over the last few years.

There are 260 weekly data from a total of 53 weeks analyzed. The data obtained is in the form of a popularity index ranging from 0-100. The higher the index indicates that the keyword search level is more popular in Indonesia.

Next, the data was analyzed using an average curve approach to determine the stages of development and decline in the trend that occurred.

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The analysis results obtained from the collected data are aggregate results for 52 weeks (1 year). There are five viral topics analyzed in this research, namely: Dalgona Coffee, Citayam Fashion Week, BTS Meal, Ice Kepal Milo and Latto-latto.

Based on the data shown in Table I, you can see every data from each topic for 52 weeks. The basis for choosing a period of 52 weeks is to make it easier for the author to carry out the analysis.

Table 1. Five Topics Data Trends Analytic

Week	BTS Meal: (Indonesia)	citayam fashion week: (Indonesia)	Dalgona coffee: (Indonesia)	es kepal milo: (Indonesia)	latto latte: (Indonesia)	AVR
1	0	0	<1	0	1	0,40
2	<1	0	0	0	<1	0,50
3	0	0	0	<1	<1	0,75
4	0	0	0	<1	<1	1,00
5	0	<1	0	0	0	1,00
6	0	0	0	0	1	1,17
7	0	0	0	0	1	1,33
8	0	0	0	0	2	1,67
9	0	0	0	1	7	2,83
10	0	<1	<1	1	7	4,50
11	0	0	<1	1	6	3,60
12	0	<1	9	2	13	7,20
13	0	0	50	5	25	15,50
14	<1	0	100	14	44	34,40
15	0	0	62	53	100	38,33
16	<1	0	37	92	99	48,80
17	<1	0	10	100	78	41,00
18	<1	<1	6	99	29	38,00
19	<1	0	5	91	20	27,00
20	<1	<1	4	52	13	22,25
21	4	0	4	34	9	12,00
22	3	0	4	22	5	9,33
23	100	0	4	18	4	24,83
24	19	<1	5	16	3	13,40
25	4	0	5	14	2	8,33
26	2	0	4	15	1	8,00
27	1	4	3	14	2	8,50
28	1	19	3	13	1	10,83
29	1	42	2	13	1	14,67
30	1	100	2	11	1	24,17
31	1	26	2	11	1	12,00
32	1	11	1	10	1	9,33
33	<1	7	1	6	1	9,60
34	1	5	1	5	1	7,83
35	<1	5	1	4	<1	11,25
36	<1	3	1	4	1	9,00
37	<1	3	1	3	1	9,00
38	<1	2	1	3	<1	11,00
39	<1	3	1	2	1	9,20
40	<1	2	1	3	1	9,40
41	<1	2	1	2	<1	11,50
42	<1	2	1	2	<1	11,75
43	<1	1	1	2	11	11,60
44	<1	1	1	2	5	10,60
45	<1	1	1	2	3	10,40
46	<1	1	1	2	2	10,40
47	<1	1	<1	1	2	12,75
48	<1	1	<1	1	3	13,25
49	<1	1	1	1	2	10,80
50	<1	1	1	1	1	10,80
51	<1	1	<1	1	1	13,50
52	<1	1	1	1	1	11,20

Source: Google Trend

The data shaded in the column shows the time the topic started to appear detected on the online platform. The background color is given to show the time range resulting from each topic. Each topic has a different start and finish time range, so to facilitate analysis the author normalizes the five topics by cutting off at the start and end points with a limit duration of 30 weeks.

The basis for selecting 30 weeks is to look at the furthest cut off obtained by one of the topics and fulfill them to make analysis easier. Normalized data can be seen in Table II. This data makes it easier for the author to analyze the stages of each week.

Table 2. Normalized Data

Week	BTS Meal: (Indonesia)	citayam fashion week: (Indonesia)	Dalgona coffee: (Indonesia)	es kepal milo: (Indonesia)	latto latte: (Indonesia)	AVR	Q	Stages
1	4	4	9	2	2	4,2	I	Introduction
2	3	19	50	5	7	16,8	II	Hyper Growth
3	100	42	100	14	7	52,6	III	Peak
4	19	100	62	53	6	48	IV	Slowing Down
5	4	26	37	92	13	34,4	IV	
6	2	11	10	100	25	29,6	IV	
7	1	7	6	99	44	31,4	IV	
8	1	5	5	91	100	40,4	IV	
9	1	5	4	52	99	32,2	IV	
10	1	3	4	34	78	24	IV	
11	1	3	4	22	29	11,8	V	
12	1	2	4	18	20	9	V	
13	1	3	5	16	13	7,6	V	
14	1	2	5	14	9	6,2	V	
15	1	2	4	15	5	5,4	V	
16	1	2	3	14	4	4,8	V	
17	1	1	3	13	3	4,2	V	
18	1	1	2	13	2	3,8	V	
19	1	1	2	11	1	3,2	V	
20	1	1	2	11	2	3,4	V	
21	1	1	1	10	1	2,8	V	
22	1	1	1	6	1	2	V	
23	1	1	1	5	1	1,8	VI	
24	1	1	1	4	1	1,6	VI	
25	1	1	1	4	1	1,6	VI	
26	1	1	1	3	1	1,4	VI	
27	1	1	1	3	1	1,4	VI	
28	1	1	1	2	1	1,2	VI	
29	1	1	1	3	1	1,4	VI	
30	1	1	1	2	1	1,2	VI	
31	1	1	1	2	1	1,2	VI	
32	1	1	1	2	1	1,2	VI	
33	1	1	1	2	1	1,2	VI	
34	1	1	1	2	1	1,2	VI	
35	1	1	1	2	1	1,2	VI	
36	1	1	1	1	1	1	VI	

From Table II it can be drawn that the stages are divided into six stages, namely: Stage I (Introduction), Stage II (Hyper Growth), Stage III (Peak), Stage IV (Slowing Down), Stage V (Bottom Line), Stage VI (End Cycle). Each stage is divided according to the average index obtained from weekly data on the five topics studied.

The peak point was obtained in the third week, with a value of 52.6. The fastest growth occurred in the second week to the third week, where there was an index of 16.8. There was fourfold growth from the first week. This growth was found in these five topics. This indicates the rapid growth of interest in digital users over time.

In the fourth to ninth weeks there were increases and decreases that were not too significant. This shows that the topic is still being discussed even though it has no longer reached its peak. This can be seen in the fourth week the index fell to 48 (and continued to fall until the seventh week) but in the eighth week there was a bounce back to 40.4. After that there was a continuous decline. The tenth week is a crucial point because after this the topic will enter the Bottom-Line stage.

Fig. 1. Trend Chart Accumulated (Source: Google Trend)

From the data analyzed, it was found that the process of decreasing (bottom line) would start from weeks ten to 22nd. There was a gradual decline in the index over that week. This indicates that this topic is experiencing a decline in interest from digital users.

Fig. 2. Trend Chart (Source: Google Trend)

If each topic is analyzed and compared (as shown in Figure 2), it is found that the topic Ice Kepala Milo and Latte latte is a topic that has a longer duration compared to the other three topics. Specifically on the topic of Milo Ice Cream which has remained on Google search media in Indonesia for a long time for approximately 21 weeks with a high index.

Fig. 3. Trend Curve (Source: Google Trend)

As depicted in Figure 3, visually the trend curve obtained is similar to a triangle. This will easily help the author explain the trend patterns that occur, at least from the five topics studied.

The Introduction Stage has a very short time span, this is possible because of the high penetration of digital media use in society. If previously communication had to go through several stages that took quite a long time, today's digital

technology capabilities and dynamic consumer behavior provide marketers with the advantage of being able to quickly disseminate information to their target market through the concept of buzz or viral marketing.

The multiple digital penetration capabilities mean that the growth of conversation in digital media is also very fast. At the next stage. In the second week, the five research object topics reached their peak. This shows how easy it is to make something viral, but also how easily it will lose consumer interest.

At the Slowing Down stage, we can see those discussions on digital media regarding this topic fade in and out. This indicates that the user is considering whether the topic is relevant for further development or not in terms of conversation. If it turns out that the topic does not add information or value, then the topic will quickly move to the bottom-line stage, the stage where a topic is heading towards its end.

V. CONCLUSION

Based on the findings written above, it can be concluded that a topic that goes viral on digital media develops very quickly but will also disappear very quickly from user conversations. To reach peak, a topic only takes about 3 weeks (21 days). This opens an opportunity for marketers to use the golden week to maximize communication targets, because after that week, the topic will begin to enter a stage where it will not return to its highest point.

With the short time available, a communication campaign must be easy for the target market to understand, and of course provide its own uniqueness to get the attention of their consumers. No topic goes viral for a whole year, so this encourages creativity so that every quarter a new and relevant marketing topic is developed to stay in the minds of consumers.

VI. LIMITATIONS

This research will require future developments, specifically from case studies of the viral topic being researched and its use by industry in accommodating the multiplication effects resulting from the conversation side in digital media. Out that the topic does not add information or value, then the topic will quickly move to the bottom-line stage, the stage where a topic is heading towards its end.

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